

EFFECT OF MATHEMATICAL LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION ON SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN "BEARING" WORD PROBLEMS IN MATHEMATICS

By

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of Mathematics Language instruction on Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 105 Senior Secondary School II Students. The selection was based on Sex and School type in Ilorin Metropolis of Kwara State. The study was a Pre-test, Post-test, non-randomize, non-equivalent quasi experimental type. The experimental group was thought a list of Mathematical terms in Bearing word Problems prior to actual teaching of the topic while the control group was taught using the Conventional lecture method. Four easy items on Bearing word Problems were drawn by the researcher from the Senior School Certificate Examination Questions and used as instrument for data collection. The formulated hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic. The result of analysis showed that the group that received treatment on teaching of the Mathematics language of Bearing Performed better than their counterparts that were not exposed. It is therefore recommended that the Mathematical language of Bearing should be first taught before engaging Students in word Problems on Bearing to enhance good Performance in the topic.

INTRODUCTION

Ojerinde (1999); Odogwu (2002) and Eguavon (2002) Conceptualized Mathematics as the Communication system of those concepts of shape, size, quantity and order used to describe diverse phenomena. Also, Onoh and Obodo (2000) defined Mathematics as a subject in which "one never knows what one talks about nor knows whether what one says is true". This means that Mathematics is a language in which its truth is dependent on the meaning assigned to the words and the symbols.

Mathematics has its own language whose terminologies are not universal to most first spoken language of different cultures in the world. For example, there are no equivalent words for factorization, function, equation and so on in most Nigeria languages (Osefehinti, 1993).

On the otherhand, Bearing could be defined as the clockwise measurement in degrees of the angular relationship between any two points in the same horizontal plane (Soyemi, 2000). Also Milligton (2005), Conceptualized Bearing as the relative direction of a line with respect to the north-south line to any point on the earth surface.

However, one of the goals of Mathematics teaching and learning is to develop the ability to recognize a Problem and apply the knowledge of Mathematics to obtain the solution to the Problem (Salman, 2002).

According to the WAEC Chief Examiner Report (1999), Student fail to attempt or fail Bearing Problem in the Senior Secondary School Examination because of their inability as a result of their inability to translate the expression (word expression) given into diagrammatical form. Therefore, Mathematical language must be accurately understood for proper understanding of Mathematics and to be able to solve "Bearing" word Problem. Such word as find the Bearing of one point to another must be accurately translated into symbol and also direction of the Bearing must be properly located. If all these were done, Students would have little or no Problem in Solving "Bearing" word Problems (Ameen, 2007).

The following Research Questions were generated.

Research Questions

- (1). what is the effect of Mathematical language on the Performance of Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics?
- (2). Is there any difference in the Performance of Male and Female Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics?
- (3). Is there any difference in the Performance of Private and Public School Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics?

Research Hypotheses

Based on questions, three research hypotheses were formulated.

H₀: Mathematical language instruction has no significant effect on Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics.

Table 1: T-test statistic on the significant effect of Mathematics language instruction based on the experimental and control groups.

Table Title

Variable	N	Means x	SD	S Error	Df	Cal test	Table to value	Decision	Remark
Experimental	60	82.75	20.03	2.59	103	7.49	1.98	H ₀ rejected	S
Control group	45	56.33	14.52	2.16					

Table 1 shows the value of t-test for the experimental and control groups. The calculated t-value is 7.49 while the table value for t-test is 1.98. Since $t > t_t$, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that Mathematical Language instructions have significant effect on the Performance of Students; both the experimental and the control groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis 1 is rejected.

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H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the Performance of Male and Female Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics.

Table 2: T-test statistic on the analysis of the significant difference between Male and Female Students

Variable	N	Means x	SD	S Error	Df	Cal test	Table to value	Decision	Remark
Male	50	91.40	20.08	2.84	98	1.60	2.00	H ₀ ₂ accepted	NS
Female	50	85.50	16.64	2.35					

Table 2 shows that the calculated t-test was 1.60 which is less than the table t-test of 2.00 at 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that there is no significant difference in the Performance of Male and Female Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 was accepted.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the Performance of Private and Public School Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics.

Table 3: t-test statistic on analysis of significant difference between Private and Public School Students.

Variable	N	Means x	SD	S Error	Df	Cal test	Table to value	Decision	Remark
Private School	50	106.70	18.53	2.62	98	2.50	2.00	H ₀ ₃ rejected	S
Public School	50	64.00	22.09	3.12					

The calculated t-value of 10.47 is greater than the table t-value of 2.01 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. This shows that there is significant difference in the Performance of Students based on the type. Therefore, the null hypothesis 3 was rejected.

Discussion

Based on the findings of the study, it was observed that there was a significant difference between the experimental group and the control group, which confirmed that when the Mathematical Language instruction in "Bearing" was explained to the Students, they Performed better than their counterparts who were taught with the use of placebo (four wooden cardinal points). Therefore, hypothesis I was rejected.

There was no difference in the Performance of Male and Female Students in Solving "Bearing" Word Problems in Mathematics and therefore, the hypothesis 2 was accepted.

Based on the hypothesis 3 stated earlier, it was further observed that School type (Private and Public Schools) have significant influence in the Performance of Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems because Students in the Private School Performed better than their counterparts in Public Schools and therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was then concluded that School type has significant influence on the Performance of Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics. It was also observed that the gender of Students do not have any influence on the Performance of the Students in Solving "Bearing" word Problems in Mathematics. Similarly, Private Schools Students responded positively and Performed better in the Performance test than their counterparts in the Public Schools.

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